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Policy Brief No. 4

Mapping The Consumer Journey In The Hotel Industry: Guest Segmentation And Experience evolution

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Further Reading:

O'Rourke, V., Rodríguez-Santos, C., Duffley, S., Costa Feito, A. and Bayram Arli, N., (2025). Mapping the consumer journey in the hotel industry: guest segmentation and experience evolution. *Consumer Behavior in Tourism and Hospitality*, pp.1-20.

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Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Accommodation experiences are multifaceted. Consumer journey mapping research generally focuses on the purchase decision or post-consumption stage in isolation. This does not adequately reflect the nature of continuous interactions in the hospitality industry. This study sought to provide a holistic analysis of the consumer journey in the luxury hotel industry. Specifically we sought to identify critical touchpoints that influence satisfaction and loyalty by analysing the entire consumer journey; to segment guests according to their satisfaction levels to understand different profiles and behaviour patterns; and to provide a comprehensive perspective on customer experience management by integrating emotional and rational factors.

Research Findings

K-means clustering identified three guest delight segments: 'Dissatisfied Seekers', 'Content but Cautious' and 'Delighted Advocates'. Results highlight differing decision-making factors, experiences and emotions encountered at various stages of the customer journey by each segment, indicating the need to develop tailored service delivery strategies. Consistent service and proactive recovery are essential to improve the experiences of 'Dissatisfied Seekers'. Consistent service, personalised touches and loyalty offers will help convert 'Content but Cautious' consumers into loyal advocates. Delighted advocates value personalised, emotionally resonant experiences that foster repeat visits and word-of-mouth. Ongoing innovation and tailored enhancements will help maintain their loyalty.

Policy Implications

The tourism sector, including luxury accommodation, is one of Ireland's largest employment sectors. Luxury hotels can act as an anchor business in regions, stimulating spending in the locality. Policymakers should prioritise subsidising professional development programmes that upskill hospitality staff in empathy and emotional engagement. Policies that support shared systems or collaborative frameworks to analyse post stay evaluations to inform policy and sector-wide benchmarking are valuable. Research grants to enable the exploration of the holistic consumer journey, tracking consumer delight over time, across stays in all hotel categories, will facilitate the development of policies that reinforce Ireland's global hospitality brand.

Industry Recommendations

'Dissatisfied Seekers' value proactive recovery and real-time feedback. Staff should identify early signs of dissatisfaction and respond empathetically. Tools including in-room surveys enable quick resolution. Acknowledging feedback and outlining improvements in post-stay follow ups rebuilds trust and fosters positive word-of-mouth. 'Content but Cautious' guests value consistency. Clear pre-arrival communication and personalised offers enhance perceived value. Loyalty programs and exclusive incentives drive repeat bookings. 'Delighted Advocates' should receive tailored benefits, unique experiences, and advocacy programs. Personalised welcomes and unique experiences reinforce their status, while public recognition further strengthens loyalty, turning them into brand ambassadors.

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